

CAUSES, FACTORS OF CHANGES IN THE MENTALITY OF STUDENTS AND YOUNG PEOPLE AND THEIR ELIMINATION IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

Based on the purpose of physical education in the continuous education system, this article shows the main tasks of physical education in terms of health, exercise, physical development, formation of movement skills and abilities of pupils and students, as well as the article describes the objective and subjective factors that have a negative and positive effect on the psyche of students and youth, and opinions on their elimination.

Key words: *Continuous education system, physical education, physical and mental capacity, personality mentality, hygienic knowledge and skills, mental and aesthetic quality, positive and negative changes.*

Today, in order to increase the quality of education and achieve efficiency, along with material factors, it is also important to develop physical education in education, to increase the physical capabilities of students and to strengthen their will. One of the urgent tasks is to create the necessary conditions for students to develop their physical abilities, achieve their mental stability, get rid of fear, unwillingness and self-doubt, as well as to become mature people and be able to function in accordance with the requirements of the time. is drinking.

The main goal of correcting the mentality of students, correcting their behavior, developing their physical and mental capabilities through physical education is to make the young generation mature in all respects, necessary for the development of our society. is to make them into perfect human beings. A perfect person embodies spiritual and physical maturity. However, due to various reasons and factors, it is observed that there are distortions and gaps in the education of young people. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the development of society. According to the head of our state, young people tend to think in a new way, boldly come up with new ideas and implement them, solve problems based on creative and non-standard approaches. That is why we give priority to the creation of all conditions for the young generation to gain knowledge, to reveal their talents and potential in the fields of science, innovation, literature, art and sports, and to actively participate in the social and political life of our society. In one of the blessed hadiths collected by our grandfather, Imam Bukhari, it is said: "The knowledge learned in youth is like a

pattern carved on stone." It is well known from history that our great scholars followed such wisdom and made great discoveries in the field of science and made an incomparable contribution to the development of universal thought. Continuing such auspicious traditions and bringing up new Khorezms, Ferghanis, Berunis, Ibn Sinas, Mirza Ulugbeks, Navoi in our country is not only our task, but also our sacred duty to history and the future" [2]. In order to fulfill this duty, it is necessary to pay attention at the level of state policy to the issue of proper upbringing of young people and raising them mentally stable.

Research on the elimination of changes in the mentality of students through physical education can be classified into three parts - studies in Western countries, CIS countries and Uzbekistan.

Gregory K. Patton, Wendell R. Gamer, S. D. Brookfield, R. M. Milgram, Drapeau Patti, Albert Bandura, researches on the development of knowledge on the psychological influence of future physical education teachers in the West along with physical education , Richard Walters, Louis Cohen can be seen in their scientific research.

In the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), a number of research works have been carried out in this regard and are still being carried out today. In particular, researchers A. Akhmatova, A. M. Derkach, A. S. Glinsky, K. M. Lulikova, I. I. Prodanov, T. V. Zobnitsa, A. M. Leontyev, G. V. Mironova, among the researchers, on strengthening the mental education of students based on physical education, and having a positive effect on their psyche issues related to the development of pedagogical approach and innovative methodology are covered.

Development of knowledge and skills of future teachers in Uzbekistan to have a positive effect on the psyche of students, especially the development of the competence of physical education teachers to integrate physical education with mental and spiritual education N.A.Muslimov, M.Isakov, R.Yusupov, A.T.Nurmanov, S.Turgunov, H.Roziyev, A.Sh.Soliyev, G.Kh.Tillayeva studied pedagogic scientists.

In the continuing education system, based on the purpose of physical education, the main tasks of physical education are defined in terms of health, exercise, physical development, and formation of movement skills and abilities of pupils and students:

Providing special knowledge about physical exercises and sports. "Physical exercise is understood as a variety of voluntary movement activities that meet the requirements of the laws of physical education and are performed

consciously. Such movement activities were systematized, collected and filled with style as gymnastics, games, sports, and tourism exercises.

Instilling hygienic knowledge and skills in students. This task is to provide pupils and students with the necessary knowledge about the benefits of physical training, compliance with hygienic rules, and the rules for correct performance of all physical exercises provided for in the program. All of these are directly related to health promotion, their knowledge of hygiene rules and their adherence to them, and this is achieved through cooperative action. Exercise and sports are taught in physical education classes, daily activities and club activities. As a result, physical development is ensured" [9:68]. Also, pupils and students are interested in sports and are attracted to sports.

Strengthening health, helping students to develop and train properly. Under the influence of natural factors, water, sun, air, students' health will be strengthened, trained, and the body will be more resistant to diseases. Carrying out physical education classes in fresh air as much as possible or organizing sports halls to be supplied with fresh air. Directing pupils and students in water treatments, swimming and bathing, and sunbathing activities. These activities are carried out as walks, excursions and tourism activities. This task is the most important of all physical culture and sports activities in an educational institution. It should be the center of attention of every teacher and team of pedagogues. Therefore, pupils and students should develop normally from a physical point of view.

Formation and improvement of movement skills and abilities, training in new movement types and movement activities. Pupils and students are regularly engaged in physical culture classes, at home, in physical culture clubs and sports clubs, systematically mastering vital movement skills such as walking, running, throwing, scrambling, balancing. All the listed activities will help in all-round physical development and preparation for cocktails. Speed, strength, agility and endurance and flexibility are qualities that everyone needs. They are intrinsically related to the formation of movement skills in pupils and students [7:67].

Education of mental and aesthetic qualities. Cultivating bravery, determination, discipline, sense of community, friendship and camaraderie, cultural behavior skills, attitude to work and social property. The whole process of physical education helps to cultivate such valuable moral and willful qualities. Many physical exercises and play activities help to develop feelings of bravery and friendship. Also, "Formation and education of love for the motherland,

patriotism, feelings. Forming the right figure. Forming the skills of correct posture while standing and walking. Educating pupils and students in a wide range of intellectual and moral aspects is one of the important tasks, because the consciousness of pupils and students is during development. The desired results can be achieved only when education is directed in a good direction" [3:126]. Education of organization in pupils and students, preparation of physical culture activities. In order to successfully carry out mass physical culture and sports activities in the educational institution, to fully conduct physical culture classes and trainings, students and students need the constant support of the physical culture activity of the teacher [4:46].

The process of teaching physical movements. Its task is to perform the action and improve it to ensure the emergence of skills [6:178]. The process of repeating this stage is repeated many times. Although each iteration looks the same on the outside, each time the content is new inside. He got something different from the previous one. Figuratively speaking, "repetition without repetition", "practice without practice" is like repetition. It is in this way that the criterion and foundation of the activity of the new movement is hidden. "It is necessary to form the spiritual feelings of the participants and to connect them with life, society, passion, and work activities. It is necessary to encourage those engaged in the process of physical education to actively participate in the struggle to build a new society. In order to educate the students in the spirit of the idea of national independence, how they live, what they think about, how they work in production, how they study at school, how they behave in the family and in public places. how to spend time and others should be fully known by physical education specialists"[5:94].

We know that the personality of a student is formed under the influence of the reality that surrounds him. As a result, he begins to understand the tasks that are socially important and enters into independent relations with other members of society, and thus the socialization of the student is completed. At the same time, the personality of the student is formed as a result of mastering the elements of social experience, receiving education, acquiring a certain specialty. Pedagogist B. Umarov puts forward the following opinion about the objective factor affecting negative changes in students' morale: "Unhealthy environment in society, conditions, economic and political instability, social problems in small social groups as objective reasons. - psychological conditions, relationships with people...[8:6]. Therefore, changes in the students' mentality are first of all caused by the unhealthy environment that surrounds them. It is known that the family

is the first center of socialization for a teenager. It is in this center that the teenager begins to interact with the social environment, learns the social norms and values of the society. Based on these, the behavior of the teenager is formed. One or another form of relations between parents, that is, peace or discord in the family, the nature of relations between brothers and sisters, are among the factors that determine the behavior of adolescents. In particular, it happens as a result of conflicts in the family, inappropriate behavior of one of the parents, and their indifference and harshness towards child upbringing. In this regard, it is enough to look at the research of the famous psychologist Getting. In his opinion, problems and conflicts in families cause aggressiveness in teenagers, especially because they grow up angry, angry and rude. According to Getting's conclusions, in conflict families, the main focus is on mutual conflicts, and child education continues to consist of threats and punishment.

Concern for the future generation, striving to raise a physically and mentally healthy generation is one of our national characteristics. Similarly, this is an important task facing every family and society today. While parents live with the dream of having a child and raising it, they want it to become a mature person, a perfect person in the future. This issue is the duty of every pedagogue and educational institution to society, and teachers, like parents, encourage their students to reach maturity. So, an intelligent child is not only a parent, but also a teacher, and the happiness of the society and the country. Therefore, it is absolutely impossible to approach such an important and strategic issue as education in the old way, with the old knowledge and system. If we do not create the most modern and advanced system in this regard, we will not be able to solve any problem facing us" [1:148]. These things cannot be done "without completely changing the society's attitude to education"[1:149].

Psychologist and scientist B. Umarov includes the following in the subjective causes of this problem: "The subjective causes of behavioral deviation include the interests and needs of the adolescent, worldview and spiritual world, goals and directions, values, legal consciousness, life plans, lifestyle and motives. Subjective conditions include demographic and socio-psychological characteristics of the population, in particular, ethno-psychological aspects, character, temperament, age and gender. Unhealthy environment in society, conditions, economic and political instability, socio-psychological conditions in small social groups, relations with people are shown as objective reasons" [7:67-68]. In the same way, we included the subjective factors of negative changes in

the psyche of students and young people: problems in the process of the formation of the adolescent personality, characteristics of their temperament. In general, changes in the mentality of students and young people are not the result of subjective behavior specific to a person, but are the result of subjective and objective factors, conditions, and relationships. The causes of negative changes in the students' mentality are caused by several factors. In our opinion, they are:

Unhealthy family environment.

Lack of parents' knowledge of the psychology and physiology of education, pedagogy.

the students' agenda is not properly organized.

It is difficult for students to adapt to any team.

Negative influence of mass media.

One of the changes in the student's mentality is the excessive strictness of the pedagogue in physical education. Choosing such a way of education without taking into account the age and psychological aspects of the student is a very wrong approach. Even in such cases, serious problems are observed in the student's psyche. That is, as a result of dissatisfaction, fear or aggression, the disturbance of the emotional state leads to a number of negative situations: excitement, depression, memory loss and so on. Of course, the disorder of the mental state, in turn, affects the physical development of the student. As a result of fear and aggression, sleep disorders, rapid fatigue, and a decrease in the immune system are observed. The fear observed in students leads to a decrease in their self-confidence, limitation of independent thinking, difficulty in adapting to any team, and aggression leads to the manifestation of vices such as aggression, quarrelsomeness, quarrelsomeness.

In the West, the authors of a number of scientific studies set themselves the complex task of studying the family and family relations system, physical education opportunities, various promotional activities, and the factors that affect the education of the student's personality in the comprehensive formation of the student. Those who tried to solve such an important and complex pedagogical-psychological social task. In these studies, effective general pedagogical, psychoprophylactic and psychological-pedagogical correction and counseling, pedagogic and student training programs, which are applied in real practical life and daily activities, have been developed and recommended. These proposed programs are used as psycho-pedagogical and methodical support for the formation of the student's personality and his role in the life of the society.

In the Western psycho-pedagogical literature, special attention is paid to issues such as changes in the psyche of students that occur due to improper interpersonal relationships. Also, in this regard, researchers have shown how positively interpersonal relationships of students affect the formation and development of a student's personality, and how interpersonal relationships definitely cause negative changes in the psyche of classmates who are studying outside of their relatives and families. compared with related cases and analyzed the reasons for such differences. As a result, it becomes clear that it is important to organize interpersonal relations between the pedagogue and the student correctly, sincerely and fairly.

In conclusion, due to the above reasons and factors, many problems arise in the psyche of students and youth. This, in turn, creates a number of tasks for members of society, in particular: pedagogues and psychologists, parents. Especially in this regard, it is desirable to further increase the effectiveness of preventive work carried out with the family, to strengthen the provision of knowledge on the psyche, physiology and pedagogy of students in higher education.

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